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Assessment of Principals Roles on the Management of School Plant in Secondary Schools in Damaturu Education Zone, Yobe State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the Principals Role Performance in the Management of School Plant in Secondary Schools in Gashua Yobe state, Nigeria. The study identified seven objectives, which include among others to: .Three research questions in line with the stated objectives were raised. Three null hypotheses were formulated and tested. The study used descriptive survey design. The population involved 18 principals, 387 teachers,150 MOE officials and 1210 PTA/SBMC officials representing 18 secondary schools across the Damaturu which gave a total of 1550. Research advisors (2006) was used to determine the sample size required for the study. The instrument used for data collection was a Likert-five-point. which is tagged Assessment of Principals Role Performance the Management of School Plant in Secondary Schools in the Damaturu zone Yobe state, Nigeria. The questionnaire was pilot tested. Using test re-tests method, it was subjected to Pearson Product Moment correlation test in order to determine the reliability coefficient of the study $p < 0.05$. The reliability coefficient of 0.89 was obtained at 0.05 level of significance. The bio data of respondents were analyzed using frequencies and percentage while the research questions were answered using frequencies, mean counts and standard deviation. All the seven hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance, using ANOVA. Findings revealed that, Principals played significant roles in ensuring proper planning of school plant in secondary schools in the Damaturu Zone; there was well organization of School Environment in Secondary Schools in the Damaturu Zone, Nigeria among others. From the findings, it was recommended that Principals should ensure proper utilization of school plants through effective and smooth running of administration in the schools, encourage the application of original school master plan while building classrooms. Also, workshops and laboratories should accommodate the student's population. Other areas include, the location of students hostels, staff quarters, administrative and teacher's offices, toilets for both teachers and students should be within the school compound among others.

Keywords: School Plant, teachers, secondary schools, principals

INTRODUCTION

Management of school plant has been an issue of concern to all and sundry in educational sector in Nigeria and most importantly in the Damaturu yobe state, Nigeria. of the country. School plants refers to the school site, the building, the playground ground, the equipment and other materials provided for effective teaching and learning. School plant is the space interpretation of the curriculum, noting that the programmes of the school are expressed through the site, the building, play grounds, the arrangement and design of the school buildings. According to Emenalo (2017) school plant is the entire scope of physical infrastructural facilities which are provided to the school (for the school) for the purpose of educating the child. In the same vein, Asiabaka (2017) described school plant to consist of all types of buildings, areas for sports and games, landscape, farms and gardens including trees and paths. Others include furniture and toilet facilities, storage facilities, transportation, Information and Communication Technology (I.C.T.), and food services among others. In addition to that, Yusuf (2018) has initiated that school plants comprises all the machineries and tools used in the workshops, in addition to duplicating machines.

Nwokike (2012) asserted that management is the live-wire of any educational establishment for the achievement of school policies and objectives and that school plant management involves effective maintenance of the school structures as well as its facilities and equipment to ensure effective teaching/learning. Also, school facilities management involves keeping records, supervision, planning, motivating students and teachers to participate in facilities maintenance and evaluating the available facilities. Management of secondary school facilities and equipment involves proper storage and security, ensuring that they are kept in good condition after usage. There should be regular repairs and maintenance, replacement of faulty ones and protection from internal and external vandalization.

Statement of the problem

In most schools, where these plants are not properly utilizations and unsecured school plant, the Principals, teachers and students become much disenchanted to administer schools diligently. Principals efforts towards achieving relative goals and objectives are often met with various constraints. The researcher's interaction with principals and teachers as well as literature evidence revealed that the conditions under which the students learn in many public schools are unhealthy and deplorable. Most of our schools have very old and dilapidated buildings, and deplorable environments, poor state of school plants which are poorly managed out of use, aged and not conducive for teaching and learning process.

Lastly, our schools in the study areas which comprise Damaturu zone yobe State suffered incessant attacks from Boko Haram terrorists which led to the distractions of school plant through provision of internally displaced persons camps within the secondary schools of the affected communities. These problems posed a numbers of challenges to the principals performing efficiency in the management of secondary schools. It is based on this background that the researcher is motivated to assess the principals role performances on the management of school plants in secondary schools in Damaturu education zone, yobe state.

Objectives of the study

The following are objectives of the study

1. determine the Principals Roles Performance on the School Plant Utilization in Secondary School in the Damaturu Zone;
2. examine the Principals Roles Performance on the School Plant Safety/Security Measures in Secondary School in the Damaturu zone yobe state, Nigeria.
3. find out the Principal Role Performance on the Establishment of School Farm and Garden in Secondary School in the Damaturu yobe state, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following are Research questions to guide the study

RQ1 To what ways does the Principal Ensure the School Plants Utilization in Secondary Schools in the Damaturu yobe state, Nigeria.

RQ2. What are the Safety/Security Measures that Principals put in place for Safe Guarding the School Plants in Secondary Schools in Damaturu Yobe state, Nigeria?

RQ3. How does the Principals' Role Performance ensure the establishment of School Farm and Garden in Secondary Schools in Damaturu zone Yobe state, Nigeria.?

METHODOLOGY

The study identified three objectives, three research questions in line with the stated objectives were raised. Three null hypotheses were formulated and tested. The study used descriptive survey design. The population involved 18 principals, 387 teachers, 150 MOE officials and 1210 PTA/SBMC officials representing 18 secondary schools across the Damaturu which gave a total of 1550. Research advisors (2006) was used to determine the sample size required for the study. The instrument used for data collection was a Likert-five-point which is tagged Assessment of Principals Role Performance the Management of School Plant in Secondary Schools in the Damaturu zone yobe state, Nigeria. The questionnaire was pilot tested. Using test re-tests method, it was subjected to Pearson Product Moment correlation test in order to determine the reliability coefficient of the study $p < 0.05$. The reliability coefficient of 0.89 was obtained at 0.05 level of significance. The bio data of respondents were analyzed using frequencies and percentage while the research questions were answered using frequencies, mean counts and standard deviation. All the seven hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance, using ANOVA

Table 1: Opinions of the Respondents on the School Plant Utilizations in Secondary School in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria

S/N	Items statement	Category of Respondents	Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
			F.	%	F.	%	F.	%
1	Principals make use of school guide line in using computers, projector and other multimedia gadgets.	Principals	44	91.7	3	6.3	1	2.1
		Teachers	160	92.0	11	6.3	3	1.7
		MOE	54	90.0	4	6.7	2	3.3
		SBMC/PTA	86	86.9	10	10.1	3	3.0
2	Principals assign specialist and expert to make use of the heavy machines in the school.	Principals	42	87.5	4	8.3	2	4.2
		Teachers	150	86.2	5	2.9	19	10.9
		MOE	51	85.0	5	8.3	4	6.7
		SBMC/PTA	83	83.8	5	5.1	11	11.1
3	Principals assign specialist and expert to make use of the heavy machines in the school.	Principals	42	87.5	5	10.4	1	2.1
		Teachers	157	90.2	16	9.2	1	0.6
		MOE	53	88.3	6	10.0	1	1.7
		SBMC/PTA	86	86.9	12	12.1	1	1.0
4	Principals make sure that the teachers and students are using toilets, water service tank, reservoir and convenient space accordingly.	Principals	43	89.6	2	4.2	3	6.3
		Teachers	161	92.5	2	1.1	11	6.3
		MOE	53	88.3	2	3.3	5	8.3
		SBMC/PTA	86	86.9	2	2.0	11	11.1
5	Principals ensure that teachers and students utilize available instructional aids, instructional materials are properly used to enhance learning in the schools.	Principals	44	91.7	2	4.2	2	4.2
		Teachers	163	93.7	9	5.2	2	1.1
		MOE	55	91.7	3	5.0	2	3.3
		SBMC/PTA	88	88.9	9	9.1	2	2.0
6	The principals make sure teachers and students make effective use of library reserve books, encyclopedias and journal.	Principals	47	97.9	1	2.1	0	0.0
		Teachers	167	96.0	7	4.0	0	0.0
		MOE	59	98.3	1	1.7	0	0.0
		SBMC/PTA	97	98.0	2	2.0	0	0.0
7	School principals ensure students are	Principals	47	97.9	0	0.0	1	2.1

	allowed to make effective use of sporting dresses, balls and shoes in the schools.	Teachers	163	93.7	3	1.7	8	4.6
		MOE	59	98.3	0	0.0	1	1.7
		SBMC/PTA	97	98.0	1	1.0	1	1.0
8	Principals encourage the students to utilise the beds, chairs and desks properly to avoid being broken.	Principals	40	83.3	7	14.6	1	2.1
		Teachers	147	84.5	8	4.6	19	10.9
		MOE	50	83.3	8	13.3	2	3.3
		SBMC/PTA	83	83.8	8	8.1	8	8.1
9	Principals ensure that all school purchases are used for the purposes for which they are meant	Principals	46	95.8	0	0.0	2	4.2
		Teachers	155	89.1	1	0.6	18	10.3
		MOE	56	93.3	0	0.0	4	6.7
		SBMC/PTA	87	87.9	1	1.0	11	11.1
10	Principals make use of the school utility bus for the purpose they are meant for.	Principals	42	87.5	3	6.3	3	6.3
		Teachers	158	90.8	11	6.3	5	2.9
		MOE	52	86.7	4	6.7	4	6.7
		SBMC/PTA	83	83.8	11	11.1	5	5.1

In response to items 1 to 10 in Table 1 which sought on the principal role performance of school plant utilization in secondary schools in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria, responses of all respondents were collected, analysed and discussed. Responses to item 1 revealed that 4 (91.7%) of principals agreed that, they make use of school guide line in using computers, projector and other multimedia gadgets, 3 (6.3%) of the principal were undecided while, 1 (2.1%) disagreed to the statement. 160 (90.0%) of teachers agreed to the statement that they make use of school guide line in using computers, projector and other multimedia gadgets, 1 (6.3%) were undecided and 3 (1.7%) disagreed. Among the officials of ministries of education (MOE), 54 (90.0%) agreed that they make use of school guide line in using computers, projector and other multimedia gadgets, however 4 (6.7%) were undecided while, 2 (3.3%) disagreed with the statement. Also, among SBMC/PTAs, 86 (86.9%) agreed that they make use of school guide line in using computers, projector and other multimedia gadgets, 10 (10.1%) were undecided with the statement. In all, it could be said that the respondents showed a greater response that principals make use of school guide line in using computers, projector and other multimedia gadgets in the secondary schools in Damaturu Zone of Nigeria. The result shows they are affirmative.

In responses to item 2, it revealed that principals assigned specialist and expert to make use of the heavy machines in the school. The result shows 42 (87.5%) of principal agreed to the statement, 4 (8.3%) undecided and 2 (4.2%) disagreed to the statement. 150 (86.2%) of teachers agreed, 5 (2.9%) undecided while, 19 (10.9%) disagreed to the statement. Among the officials of Ministries of Education (MOE), 51 (85.0%) agreed that principals assigned specialist and expert to make use of the heavy machines in the school while, 4 (4.0%) disagreed. Among SBMC/PTA members, the result shows that 83 (83.8%) agreed that principals assigned specialist and expert to make use of the heavy machines in the school, 5 (5.1%) undecided and 11 (11.1%) disagreed with the statement. In all, the respondents showed a greater magnitude of their response that principals assigned specialist and expert to make use of the heavy machines in secondary schools in the Damaturu Zone of Nigeria. The result shows they are affirmative.

In responses to item 4, it was revealed that principals make sure the teachers and students are using toilets, water service tank, reservoir and convenient space accordingly in secondary schools in Damaturu zone. The result shows 43 (89.6%) of principals agreed to the statement, 2 (4.2%) undecided, 3 (6.3%) disagreed to the statement. 161 (92.5%) of teachers agreed that principals make sure the teachers and students are using toilets, water service tank, reservoir and convenient space accordingly in secondary schools in Damaturu zone while 11 (6.3%) disagreed to the statement. Among the officials of Ministries of education (MOE), 53 (88.3%) agreed that principals make sure the teachers and students are using toilets, water service tank, reservoir and convenient space accordingly in secondary schools in Damaturu zone, 2 (3.3%) were undecided while 5 (8.3%) disagreed with the statement. Among SBMC/PTA members, the result shows that 86 (86.9%) agreed that principals make sure the teachers and students are using toilets, water service tank, reservoir and convenient space accordingly in secondary schools in North-East zone, 2 (2.0%) were undecided with the statement while 11 (11.1%) disagreed. In all, the respondents showed a greater magnitude of their responses that principals make sure the teachers and students are using toilets, water service tank, reservoir and convenient space accordingly in secondary schools in Damaturu zone of Nigeria. The result shows they are affirmative.

In responses to item 5, it was revealed that principals ensure that teachers and students utilize available instructional aids, instructional materials are properly used to enhance learning in the schools. The result shows 44 (91.7%) of

principals agreed to the statement while, 2 (4.2%) were undecided and disagreed with the statement respectively. 163 (93.7%) of teachers agreed, 9 (5.2%) were undecided. Among the officials of ministries of education (MOE), 55 (91.7%) agreed that principals ensure that teachers and students utilize available instructional aids, instructional materials are properly used to enhance learning in the schools while, 2 (1.1%) disagreed with the statement. Also, from the opinions of SBMC/PTA members, the result shows that 88 (88.9%) agreed to the statement, 9 (9.1%) were undecided while, 2 (2.0%) disagreed with the statement. In all, the respondents showed a greater magnitude of their responses that principals ensure that teachers and students utilize available instructional aids, instructional materials are properly used to enhance learning in secondary schools in the Damaturu Zone of Nigeria. The result shows they are affirmative.

Going by the respondents opinions on items 6 to 10 where no respondent had less than 83.3% in respect of disagreement, it is evident that there was a positive perception from the respondents toward principal role performance of school plant utilization in secondary schools in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria. It is believed that, principals make sure teachers and students make effective use of library reserve books, encyclopedias and journal, School principals ensures students are allowed to make effective use of sporting dresses, balls and shoes in the schools, Principals encourage the students to utilise the beds, chairs and desks properly to avoid being broken, principals ensure that all school purchases are used for the purposes for which they are meant and principals make use of the school utility bus for the purpose they are meant for in secondary schools in the Damaturu Zone, Nigeria.

Opinions of the Respondents on the principal role performance on the school plant safety/security measures in secondary schools in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria

In this section, the opinions of respondents were sought on the principals role performance on the school plantsafety/security measures in secondary schools in Damaturu Zone of Nigeria. This section relates to research question one which asks what are the opinions of principals, teachers, PTA/SBMC and Ministry of Education officials on principal role performance on the school plant safety/security measures in secondary schools in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria.

To answer this research question, opinions of all respondents related to items 51-60 in the questionnaire were collected, analysed and discussed using frequency counts and percentages. Thus, Table 2 gives the details.

Table 2: Opinions of the Respondents on the School Plant Safety/Security Measures in Secondary School in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria

S/N	Items Statement	Category of Respondents	Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
			F.	%	F.	%	F.	%
11	Principals introduces staff and student's identification card to control movement in the school compound.	Principals	46	95.8	0	0.0	2	4.2
		Teachers	169	97.1	0	0.0	5	2.9
		MOE	56	93.3	0	0.0	4	6.7
		SBMC/PTA	94	94.9	5	5.1	0	0.0
12	Principals makes use of security men at the gate to check any vehicle in and out the school compound.	Principals	46	95.8	0	0.0	2	4.2
		Teachers	159	91.4	4	2.3	11	6.3
		MOE	56	93.3	0	0.0	4	6.7
		SBMC/PTA	88	88.9	0	0.0	11	11.1
13	Principals install camera, security light and security men to be going around within the school compound.	Principals	45	93.8	1	2.1	2	4.2
		Teachers	161	92.5	3	1.7	10	5.7
		MOE	54	90.0	2	3.3	4	6.7
		SBMC/PTA	86	86.9	3	3.0	10	10.1
14	Principals introduce control card for borrowing of books, magazine, journal, chairs and canopy owned by the school to avoid missing.	Principals	45	93.8	1	2.1	2	4.2
		Teachers	154	88.5	6	3.4	14	8.0
		MOE	54	90.0	2	3.3	4	6.7
		SBMC/PTA	86	86.9	3	3.0	10	10.1
15	Principals check hostel by hostel, and room by room in the night in order to ensure the security of the school.	Principals	48	100	0	0.0	0	0.0
		Teachers	170	97.7	0	0.0	4	2.3
		MOE	60	100	0	0.0	0	0.0
		SBMC/PTA	99	100	99	100	99	100
16	Principals ensures that the school	Principals	48	100	0	0.0	0	0.0

	compound is fenced for proper security.	Teachers	174	100	0	0.0	0	0.0
		MOE	60	100	0	0.0	0	0.0
		SBMC/PTA	99	100	99	100	99	100
17	School principals keep proper inventory of the computers, projector and micros cope to avoid being stolen.	Principals	47	97.9	1	2.1	0	0.0
		Teachers	172	98.9	2	1.1	0	0.0
		MOE	58	96.7	2	3.3	0	0.0
		SBMC/PTA	97	98.0	2	2.0	0	0.0
18	The principal assigns to laboratory technician areas of responsibility in securing laboratory equipment.	Principals	45	93.8	0	0.0	3	6.3
		Teachers	166	95.4	0	0.0	4	2.3
		MOE	56	93.3	0	0.0	4	6.7
		SBMC/PTA	95	96.0	0	0.0	4	4.0
19	Principals appoint staff monitoring committee for the workshop machines to avoid being stolen	Principals	47	97.9	1	2.1	0	0.0
		Teachers	170	97.7	0	0.0	4	2.3
		MOE	58	96.7	2	3.3	0	0.0
		SBMC/PTA	91	91.9	8	8.1	0	0.0
20	Principals assigns cleaners to clean, trim the flowers and spray insecticide to kill all dangerous insects in school landscape.	Principals	46	95.8	2	4.2	0	0.0
		Teachers	160	92.0	10	5.7	4	2.3
		MOE	56	93.3	4	6.7	0	0.0
		SBMC/PTA	89	89.9	10	10.1	0	0.0

In response to items 11 to 22 in Table 7 which sought on the principal role performance of school plant safety/security measures in secondary schools in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria, responses of all respondents were collected, analysed and discussed.

Responses to item 11 revealed that 16 (95.8%) of principals agreed that, they introduced staff and students identification card to control movement in the school compound while, 2 (4.2%) disagreed to the statement. 169 (97.1%) of teachers agreed to the statement that they introduced staff and students identification card to control movement in the school compound and 4 (6.7%) disagreed. Among the officials of ministries of education (MOE), 56 (93.3%) agreed that they introduced staff and students identification card to control movement in the school compound, however 4 (6.7%) disagreed with the statement. Also, among SBMC/PTAs, 94 (94.9%) agreed that they introduced staff and students identification card to control movement in the school compound, 5 (5.1%) were undecided with the statement. In all, it could be said that the respondents showed a greater response that principals introduced staff and students identification card to control movement in the school compound in the secondary schools in Damaturu Zone of Nigeria. The result shows they are affirmative.

In responses to item 12, it revealed that principals make use of security men at the gate to check any vehicle in and out the school compound. The result shows 46 (95.8%) of principal agreed to the statement and 2 (4.2%) disagreed to the statement. 159 (91.4%) of teachers agreed, 4 (2.3%) undecided while, 11 (6.3%) disagreed to the statement. Among the officials of ministries of education (MOE), 56 (93.3%) agreed that principals make use of security men at the gate to check any vehicle in and out the school compound while, 4 (4.0%) disagreed. Among SBMC/PTA members, the result shows that 88 (88.9%) agreed that principals make use of security men at the gate to check any vehicle in and out the school compound and 11 (11.1%) disagreed with the statement. In all, the respondents showed a greater magnitude of their response that principals make use of security men at the gate to check any vehicle in and out the school compound in secondary schools in the Damaturu Zone of Nigeria. The result shows they are affirmative.

In responses to item 14, it was revealed that principals introduce control card for borrowing of books, magazine, journal, chairs and canopy owned by the school to avoid missing in most secondary schools in North-East zone. The result shows 45 (93.8%) of principals agreed to the statement, 1 (2.1%) undecided, 2 (4.2%) disagreed to the statement. 154 (88.5%) of teachers agreed that principals introduce control card for borrowing of books, magazine, journal, chairs and canopy owned by the school to avoid missing in most secondary schools in Damaturu zone while 14 (8.0%) disagreed to the statement. Among the officials of Ministries of Education (MOE), 54 (90.0%) agreed that principals introduce control card for borrowing of books, magazine, journal, chairs and canopy owned by the school to avoid missing in most secondary schools in North-East zone, 2 (3.3%) were undecided while 4 (6.7%) disagreed with the statement. Among SBMC/PTA members, the result shows that 86 (86.9%) agreed that principals introduce control card for borrowing of books, magazine, journal, chairs and canopy owned by the school to avoid missing in most secondary schools in Damaturu zone, 3 (3.0%) were undecided with the statement while 10 (10.1%) disagreed. In all, the respondents showed a greater magnitude of their responses that principals introduce control card for

borrowing of books, magazine, journal, chairs and canopy owned by the school to avoid missing in most secondary schools in Damaturu zone of Nigeria. The result shows they are affirmative.

In responses to item 15, it was revealed that principals check hostels by hostel, and room by room in the night in order to ensure the security of the school. The result shows 48 (100%) of principals all agreed to the statement. 170 (97.7%) of teachers agreed, 4 (2.3%) disagreed. Among the officials of Ministries of Education (MOE), 60 (100%) all agreed that principals check hostels by hostel, and room by room in the night in order to ensure the security of the school. Also, from the opinions of SBMC/PTA members, the result shows that 99 (100%) all agreed to the statement. In all, the respondents showed a greater magnitude of their responses that principals check hostels by hostel, and room by room in the night in order to ensure the security of the school in Damaturu Zone of Nigeria. The result shows they are affirmative.

Going by the respondents opinions on items 16 to 20 where no respondent had less than 89.9% in respect of disagreement, it is evident that there was a positive perception from the respondents toward principals role performance of school plant safety/security measures in secondary schools in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria. It is believed that, principals should ensure that the school compound is fenced for proper security, school principals keep proper inventory of the computers, projector and micros cope to avoid being stolen, principals appoint staff monitoring committee for the workshop machines to avoid being stolen and principals assigned cleaners to clean, trim the flowers and spray insecticide to kill all dangerous insects in school landscape in secondary schools in the Damaturu Zone, Nigeria.

Opinions of the Respondents on the principal role performance on the establishment of school form and garden in secondary schools in Danaturu Zone, Nigeria

In this section, the opinions of respondents were sought on the principal role performance on the establishment of school form and garden in secondary schools in Damaturu Zone of Nigeria. This section relates to research question one which asks what are the opinions of principals, teachers, PTA/SBMC and Ministry of Education officials on principal role performance on the establishment of school form and garden in secondary schools in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria.

To answer this research question, opinions of all respondents related to items 61-70 in the questionnaire were collected, analysed and discussed using frequency counts and percentages. Thus, Table 3 gives the details.

Table :3 Opinions of the Respondents on the Establishment of School farm/garden in Secondary School in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria

S/N	Items statement	Category of Respondents	Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
			F.	%	F.	%	F.	%
21	Principals make sell of the farm/garden products to generate money for the school.	Principals	31	64.6	5	10.4	12	25.0
		Teachers	107	61.5	17	9.8	50	28.7
		MOE	37	61.7	5	8.3	18	30.0
		PTA	68	68.7	5	5.1	26	26.3
22	Principals store and control the farm/garden products to avoid being damaged.	Principals	36	75.0	1	2.1	11	22.9
		Teachers	111	63.8	11	6.3	52	29.9
		MOE	43	71.7	1	1.7	16	26.7
		PTA	74	74.7	1	1.0	24	24.2
23	Principals contract nursery centre for the production of seedling.	Principals	32	66.7	2	4.2	14	29.2
		Teachers	105	60.3	13	7.5	58	32.2
		MOE	37	61.7	2	3.3	21	35.0
		PTA	68	68.7	2	2.0	29	29.3
24	Principals make use of modern machine such as harvesting machine; sprayer and others for school farm/garden use.	Principals	34	70.8	5	10.4	9	18.8
		Teachers	110	63.2	14	8.0	50	28.7
		MOE	40	66.7	6	10.0	14	23.3
		PTA	79	70.7	7	7.1	22	22.2
25	Principals supervise schools garden/farm regularly to determine the strength and weakness of the farming activities.	Principals	34	70.8	3	6.3	11	22.9
		Teachers	117	67.2	17	9.8	40	23.0
		MOE	40	66.7	4	6.7	16	26.7
		PTA	76	76.8	6	6.1	17	17.2

26	Principals appoint students as a conservation prefect to assist in taking care of the farming/garden activities and other related matters.	Principals	43	89.6	5	10.4	0	0.0
		Teachers	164	94.3	10	5.7	0	0.0
		MOE	54	90.0	6	10.0	0	0.0
		PTA	93	93.9	6	6.1	0	0.0
27	Principals receive report on the progress of the school garden/ farm.	Principals	45	93.6	3	6.3	0	0.0
		Teachers	168	96.6	6	3.4	0	0.0
		MOE	56	93.3	4	6.7	0	0.0
		PTA	93	93.9	6	6.1	0	0.0
28	Principals organize competition on farming/ garden activities.	Principals	46	95.8	2	4.2	0	0.0
		Teachers	165	94.8	9	5.2	0	0.0
		MOE	57	95.0	3	5.0	0	0.0
		PTA	90	90.0	9	9.	0	0.0
29	Principals export farm/garden products to the neighboring market for sell.	Principals	42	87.5	6	12.6	0	0.0
		Teachers	154	88.5	16	9.2	4	2.3
		MOE	52	86.7	8	13.3	0	0.0
		PTA	83	83.8	0	0.0	16	16.2
30	Principals assign the schools agriculture master to attend annual farm/garden.	Principals	47	97.9	1	2.1	0	0.0
		Teachers	172	98.9	2	1.1	0	0.0
		MOE	58	96.7	2	3.3	0	0.0
		PTA	97	98.0	2	2.0	0	0.0

In response to items 21 to 30 in Table 4.8 which sought on the principal role performance of establishment of school farm and garden in secondary schools in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria, responses of all respondents were collected, analysed and discussed.

Responses to item 21 reveals that 31 (64.6%) of principals agreed that, they make sell of the farm/garden products to generate money for the school, 5 (10.4%) undecided while, 12 (25.0%) disagreed to the statement. 107 (61.5%) of teachers agreed to the statement that they make sell of the farm/garden products to generate money for the school, 17 (9.8%) undecided and 50 (28.7%) disagreed. Among the officials of ministries of education (MOE), 37 (61.7%) agreed that they make sell of the farm/garden products to generate money for the school. However, 18 (30.0%) disagreed with the statement. Also, among SBMC/PTAs, 68 (68.7%) agreed that they make sell of the farm/garden products to generate money for the school, 5 (5.1%) were undecided and 26 (26.3%) disagreed with the statement. In all, it could be said that the respondents showed a greater response that principals make sell of the farm/garden products to generate money for the school in the secondary schools in Damaturu Zone of Nigeria. The result shows they are affirmative.

In responses to item 22, it reveals that principals store and control the farm/garden products to avoid being damaged. The result shows 36 (75.0%) of principal agreed to the statement and 1 (22.9%) disagreed to the statement. 111 (63.8%) of teachers agreed, 11 (6.3%) undecided while, 52 (29.9%) disagreed to the statement. Among the officials of ministries of education (MOE), 43 (71.7%) agreed that principals store and control the farm/garden products to avoid being damaged while, 16 (26.7%) disagreed. Among SBMC/PTA members, the result shows that 74 (74.7%) agreed that principals store and control the farm/garden products to avoid being damaged and 24 (24.2%) disagreed with the statement. In all, the respondents showed a greater magnitude of their response that principals make use of security men at the gate to check any vehicle in and out the school compound in secondary schools in the Damaturu Zone of Nigeria. The result shows they are affirmative.

In responses to item 24, it was revealed that principals make use of modern machine such as harvesting machine; sprayer and others for school farm/garden use in most secondary schools in zone. The result shows 34 (70.8%) of principals agreed to the statement, 5 (10.4%) undecided, 9 (18.8%) disagreed to the statement. 110 (63.2%) of teachers agreed that principals make use of modern machine such as harvesting machine; sprayer and others for school farm/garden use in most secondary schools in Damaturu zone while, 50 (28.7%) disagreed to the statement. Among the officials of ministries of education (MOE), 40 (66.7%) agreed that principals make use of modern machine such as harvesting machine; sprayer and others for school farm/garden use in most secondary schools in Damaturu zone, 6 (10.0%) were undecided while 14 (23.3%) disagreed with the statement. Among SBMC/PTA members, the result shows that 79 (70.0%) agreed that principals make use of modern machine such as harvesting

machine; sprayer and others for school farm/garden use in most secondary schools in Damaturu zone, 7 (7.1%) were undecided with the statement while 22 (22.2%) disagreed. In all, the respondents showed a greater magnitude of their responses that principals make use of modern machine such as harvesting machine; sprayer and others for school farm/garden use in most secondary schools in Damaturu zone of Nigeria. The result shows they are affirmative.

Going by the respondents opinions on items 25 to 30 where no respondent had less than 83.8% in respect of disagreement, it is evident that there was a positive perception from the respondents toward principal role performance of establishment of school form and garden in secondary schools in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria. It is believed that, principals appoint students as a conservation prefect to assist in taking care of the farming/garden activities, principals receive report on the progress of the school garden/ farm, principals organized competition on farming/ garden activities and principals assigns the schools agriculture master to attend annual farm/garden festival in most of the secondary schools in the Damaturu Zone, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

- * determine the principals roles performance on the school plant utilization in secondary school in the Damaturu Zone of Nigeria;
- * examine the principals roles performance on the school plant safety/security measures in secondary school in the Damaturu Zone of Nigeria;
- * find out the principal role performance on the establishment of school form and garden in secondary school in the Damaturu Zone of Nigeria.

The findings from research question five showed that the principals ensured effective utilization of school plants through such ways as: using them for teaching and learning in the schools, encouraging teachers to making appropriate use of teaching aids, and ensuring that the students make good use of library, laboratory, halls and classrooms. Other areas include: encouraging the students and teachers to make use of guidelines while operating computers, projectors and other multimedia gadgets. Making judicious use of instructional aids, instructional materials and school utility bus. The result leading to this research question shows the calculated p-value of .073 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, while the calculated F- ratio value of 0.719 is less than f-critical value of 3.10. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{04}) was retained. It could be concluded that there were no significant differences in the opinions of principals, teachers, ministry of education officials and SBMC/PTA in respect of the principals role performances on the school plant utilization in secondary schools in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria.

This was supported by Ajaredi (2010) who opined that using the school plant for educational purposes requires careful direction or much of its effectiveness can be lost. If the design of a school plant follows function, then the type of activity specified for the school plant should be taking place in that plant otherwise the plant is being incorrectly used School plant is a costly investment which must be protected by the principal careful and proper operation and utilization.

Results from research question six revealed that the school authorities ensured the safety/security of the school plants by fencing the compounds, keeping proper inventories, assigning teachers to areas of school plant maintenance and appointing committees to oversee school plants. Others include: giving students some responsibilities for maintaining school plants and ensuring that storage facilities are provided for safety/security. The result leading to this research question shows the calculated p-value of .001 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, while the calculated F- ratio value of 3.019 is greater than f-critical value of 1.32. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{06}) was rejected. It could be concluded that there was a significant difference in the opinions of principals, teachers, ministry of education officials and SBMC/PTA in respect of the principals role performances on the school plant safety/security measure in secondary schools in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria. To ascertain the extent of differences scheffes test was employed.

This was also supported by Lambard and Kole (2008) who opines that an unsafe school environment will undoubtedly, undermine the teachers authority and prevent him/her from exercising the right to impact effectively on the learners. The school management should be aware of the potential dangers that the learners could be involved in, and then take preventive steps for learners from being harmed. Thus, when

the rights of the teachers and learners are respected, it will go a long way to improve on the safety and security of the learners.

The findings from research question seven showed that the principals faced challenge on establishment of school farm/garden through constructions and development of nursery for production and distributions of seed and seedling, make use of modern machine, sprayer and chemicals. Other area making a proper supervision of school farm/garden and assign responsibilities to the teacher and students. The result of this research question shows the calculated p-value of .062 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, while the calculated F- ratio value of 0.108 is less than f-critical value of 2.18. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{07}) was retained. It could be concluded that there were no significant differences in the opinions of principals, teachers, ministry of education officials and SBMC/PTA in respect of the principals role performances on the establishment of school farm and garden in secondary schools in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria.

This was supported by Paul (2015) who opines that School farm/garden planning is a deliberate attempt by the principal to arrange and document school farm/garden activities in order, before implementing them. It is similar to the activities of a teacher in developing his lesson plan before entering the classroom to teach. The planning activities of the principal guide the teacher and consider certain things such as the farmland and its topography, the crop, raising seedling for garden to grow or livestock to rear, resources or school plant input to be made available for success in the farm/garden operations, market demands for the crop and livestock to be produced, and the practical content of the school agricultural syllabus.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that:

Stakeholders in the area of coverage of this research perceived the principals role performance on management of school plant in secondary schools of Damaturu zone, Nigeria. It was however, concluded that: Principals ensured effective utilizations of school plant in secondary schools in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria. Also, principals ensure that all school purchases are used for the purposes for which they are meant.

Principals play significant roles on ensuring tied security and safety measured were provided by introducing staff and students identification card to control movement of in and out of everyone in the secondary schools in Damaturu Zone, Nigeria.

Lastly, there were challenges faced by most principals on establishment of school farm/garden, though they usually store and control the farm/garden products to avoid being damaged and at end make sell of the farm/garden products to generate money for the schools in the Damaturu Zone, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. In order to facilitate effectively supervised and monitored the used of school facilities, school equipment and other materials to avoided mismanagement, to encourage principals to ensure the teachers, students ,school technician make effective use of school equipment, and other materials such as; school library, computers, projector and other multimedia gadgets in teaching and learning. Beds, chairs and desks should also properly used to avoid being broken. Also, ensure that playgrounds are properly used by students for sports and games purpose;
2. Principals should improved the safety/security measures in safe guarding school , teachers and students lives and property, school provide modern gadgets such as CCTV camera ,security light as well as fencing the school environment. principals should actively involved voluntarily community security guard to ensured tied security and safety in the school. and
3. In order to saved the school farm/garden product, principals should provide adequate storage facilities and make used of insecticide, herbicide for pest and diseases control as well as provision of modern storage facilities in the school.

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